

**Report
on
Seed Diversity, Germination, Plant Standing and Harvesting**

**PART- 1
KHARIF SEASON**

**State Name: West Bengal
Third Reintroduction of Farmer's Varieties
2022-2023**

Fig.: Black Gram Field of Mr. Sakila Oraon (left) and Lachhu Oraon (Right)

**Submitted To
FAO, ITPGRFA IV CYCLE PROJECT**

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Under the project

Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population.

KHARIF SEASON

Seed Biodiversity Report

Time Period for Sowing: June/July 2022

Sowing Season June 2022, WB											
WB, Re-Introduction of Crop_June 2022											
S.No.		Crop Name	Variety Name	Type of Variety	Seeds In Bank for Re-Intro	Seed destroyed / damaged in seed bank 2021-022	Seeds from Haat	Seed from Market/KVK	Purchase from farmer 022	Trial Plot and Reporting (Account No.)	Distributed to Account No.
1	Arhar	Arhar	Re-introduction 1. Maynaguri block variety	Local	5 kg	3 kg	0	0	0	Ashok Oraon (2 kg)	Dina Roy Priyabrata Roy
		Arhar	2. Batabari-block variety	Local	2.5 kg	1.5 kg	0	0	0	Jitu lohar (1 kg)	Jitu Loхар Pintu Hembraham
		Arhar	Introduction Bihar's project site variety imported 3. Ratan*	Improved	2kg	0	0	0	0	Nobir Hossain (1kg)	Anabul Islam, Dipak Roy
2	Urad / Black Gram	Urad	Re-introduction 1. IPU-02-43*	Improved	0	0	0	12 kg	0	Jitu lohar (6kg)	Dipok Roy (3kg) Suvolaxmi Roy(3kg) Rina oraon (2kg)
			2. Haat-Metali	Improved	10kg	3kg	0	0	11kg X 150 Rs (Debojit Roy) = 1650 Rs	Mithun oraon (3kg)	Asraful islam (3kg) Bhaleswari Roy (3kg) Najrul islam (3kg) Nobir Hussain (3kg) Pradip oraon (3kg)

			3. Farmer variety	Local (Mithun oraon)	7 kg	1 kg	0	0	6 kg	Dipen Barman(3kg)	Bikash Barman(3kg) Patiram Oraon(3kg) Anita Roy (3kg)
				Total	26.5 kg	8.5 kg		12 kg	17 Kg		
					Total Seed in Circulation in June =						
					26.5 kg + 12 kg+ 17 kg = 55 Kg						
				Sowing Season August 2022, WB							
WB, Re-Introduction of Crop_August 2022											
	Ragi	Ragi	Haat	Improved	3	0	0	0	0		
	Red Lentil / Masoor	Masoor	Reintroduction 1. Pusa Ageti*	Improved	0.6	0	0	0	0		
			2. Amarjyoti / Purna Chetri	Local	0.75	0	0	0	0		
			3. Pundabari Haa	Local	0.5	0	0	0	0		

Seed Distribution in field West Bengal

Dated	Activities	Outcomes
7/7/2022	Farmers field visit	Arhar seeds distribution (Ratan variety) to Nabir Hossain, CSB a/c=735206-01-0115 as a trial
8/7/2022	Farmers field visit	Arhar seeds distribution (Maynaguri variety) to Ashok Oraon, A/c=735206-01-0010 as a trial
9/7/2022	Farmers field visit	Arhar seeds distribution (Batabari hat variety) to Jitu Lohar A/c=735206-01-0032 as a trial.
12/7/2022	Farmers field visit	Arhar sowing at trail plot of Nabir Hussain
13/7/2022	Farmers field visit	Arhar sowing trail plot of Ashok Oraon
14/7/2022	Farmers field visit	Arhar sowing trail plot of Jitu Lohar

17/7/2022	Farmers field visit	Re-sowing of arhar trail of Ashok Oraon (Due to excess rain, the pulse seeds were damaged)
27/7/2022	Farmers field visit	Arhar germinated at trail plot no 1 (Ashok Lohar)
28/7/2022	Farmers field visit	Arhar germinated at trail plot no 3 (Jitu lohar)
30/7/2022	Farmers field visit	Arhar germinated at trail plot no 2 (Nabir Hossain)

Germination report:

Crop: Arhar

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 735206-01-0115)

Passbook No.	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing date	Date of Germination 50%	Any pest attack	Water logging	Other vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestions
735206-01-0115	Arhar	Ratan (Farmer variety)	12/07/2022	27/07/2022	No	Yes	No	Improve water drainage system to avoid the water logging.
735206-01-0010	Arhar	Maynaguri (Haat variety)	13/07/2022	27/07/2022	No	Yes	No	
735206-01-0032	Arhar	Batabari (Haat variety)	14/07/2022	27/07/2022	No	Yes	No	
735206-01-00115	Arhar	Ratan (Farmer variety)	Re-showing 17/07/2022	30/07/2022	No	No	No	

1. Scientist field visit date: Over phone

2. New Passbook opened: 2

3. Total beneficiary within the season: 12

4. Parceled the seed sample in PAIRVI Office: No

5. Please attach the Field visit report with good images of crop

5a. For sowing the 50 % Germination

5b. Interview of farmers in the field about 1. the characterization of crop/variety 2. Why popular specific variety in the field.

Plant Standing report:

**Crop: Black Gram,
Trials on farmer's field**

Field Visit and collecting the data for Plant standing.

Dated	Activities	Outcomes
03/10/22	Farmers field visit	Black gram field visit at Subholaxmi Roy. Very good growth and farmer is expecting good yield.
05/10/22	Farmer household visit	New CSB account opening with farmer, Sirajul Haque and Safia Begam.
06/10/22	-do-	New CSB account opening with farmer Kabir Islam.
07/10/22	Farmers field visit	Inspection of Black gram field of farmer, Bhaleswari Roy. Good growth and expected to get good return
08/10/22	Farmers households visit	New CSB account opening of farmers, Maminur Islam and Sanjukta Roy.
10/10/22	Farmers field visit	New CSB account opening of farmers, Najrul Islam and Sahar Ali.
13/10/22	Farmers field visit	Black gram field of Sakila Oraon. Very good crop and expecting to get good yield.
18/10/22	Farmers field visit	Inspection of black gram field of Lachhu Oraon. Good growth but suggested remove weeds.
26/10/22	Farmers field visit	Inspection of black gram field of Jhoru Md. Need to harvest in 1 st week of November 2022.
28/10/22	Farmers field visit	Monitoring of black gram field of Mithun Oraon.
31/10/22	Meeting	Farmers field supervision and farmers meeting.

Photos 1 & 2: Black gram field visit at Suvolaxmi Roy (left) and Bhaleswari Roy.

Photos 3&4: Black gram field visit of Sakila Oraon (left) and Lachhu Oraon.

Photos 5&6: Black gram field visit of Jhoru Md (left) and Mithun Oraon

Pod and Harvesting report:

Crop: Black Gram

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 735206-01-0032)

Trial Plot No./Passbook no.	Crop Name variety name	Pod appearing date/	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed in plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of Pod and No of Seed in pod	Other Vulnerable Factor
735206-01-0032	Improved variety 1PU-02-43	23/10/22	7	38	No	28/11/22	29 kg	Blackish and standard size.	Open grazing is major issue.
735206-01-0095	Local hat variety – Haldibari hat	24/10/22	6	34	No	29/11/22	18 kg	Blackish and smaller size	
735206-01-0120	Farmer variety – Mithun Oraon	24/10/22	6	29	No	30/11/22	15 kg	Blackish and standard size.	

Scientist Present there: Yes

1. Sequence of Trial plot No. for Best Growth:

Best growth 735206-01-0032; **Less growth** 735206-01-120

2. Trial Farm with SAME/EQUAL farmers' varieties:

Identified Characteristics

Black gram	(seed size, seed color, Plant size and color, Branches, Hairy stem or leaves and others, Flowering time)
1. Tishi- Improved variety	Blackish and standard size seeds. Plants height 22 inch
2. Tishi- Haat variety	Blackish and smaller size seeds, plant height 18 inch
3. Farmer variety	Blackish and standard size seeds, plant height 18 inch

Dated	Activities	Outcomes
04/10/22	Project field visit	Black gram seed collection from farmer, Dipak Roy.
11/11/22	-do-	Maize seeds collection from farmer, Dipak Roy
14/11/22	-do-	Visit of Agriculture Extension Officer and lentil seed sowing in the field of farmer, Sofia Begam.
15/11/22	-do-	Maize seed distribution to the farmers.
17/11/22	-do-	Yellow mustard seeds distribution to the farmer, Kabir Alam
18/11/22	-do-	Black mustard distribution to farmer, Sahar Ali.
21/11/22	-do-	Mustard sowing in the field of Nazrul Haq
25/11/22	-do-	Mustard sowing in the field of farmer, Tezbahadur Sonar.
26/11/22	-do-	Seeds sowing to farmer field.
27/11/22	-do-	Mustard field inspection – good percentage (above 80%) of germination in the field of Tez Bahadur Sonar
28/11/22	Farmers Household visit	Visit to the farmers and invitation for training and exposure conducted by PAIRVI.
30/11/22	Farmers Exposure	Farmer's field exchange visit in Alipurduar district. The knowledge of diversified crops cultivation, water management and farmers institution building enhanced among the project lead farmers.

Fencing for 3 trial plots of Arhar, July 2022, West Bengal

Farmer's field	No. of Labor	No. of Days	Labour cost	Output= Total Length of Boundary	July Trial plot introduced and reporting	Passbook No.
Ashok Oraon	3	5	5250.00	540 ft	Yes	735206-01-0010
Nabir Hossain	3	6	6950.00	670 ft	Yes	735206-01-0115
Jitu Lohar	3	5	5550.00	580 ft	Yes	735206-01-0032

Photos: Ashok Oraon, Trail plot no -1

Photos: Ashok Oraon, Trail plot no -1

Nabir Hussain, trail plots no -2

Photos: Jitu Lohar, trail plot no -3
